

Use of Balaban F and G indices in QSAR : Modeling of mutagenicity of aromatic and heteroaromatic amines[†]

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Abstract : The recently introduced Balaban F and G indices are used for modeling mutagenicity of 95 aromatic and heteroaromatic amines acting on *Salmonella typhimurium*. The correlation potential of both these indices with J index is first investigated and then their combinations are used for the mutagenic activity. The results are finally discussed using Ridge statistics.

Keywords : Mutagenicity, QSAR, topological index, Balaban type indices, heteroaromatic amine, hydrophobicity, aromatic amine.

Introduction

Topological indices are numbers associated with molecular graphs for the purpose of allowing quantitative structure-activity/property/toxicity relationships¹⁻⁴. In hydrogen-depleted (or hydrogen-suppressed) molecular graphs, vertices symbolize non-hydrogen atoms, and edges symbolize covalent bonds, and such graphs are the every-day formulas of organic compounds. The first topological index *W* was introduced by Harold Wiener and bears his name⁵. For trees (acyclic graphs) Wiener defined *W* as the sum of products of the numbers of vertices on the two sides of each edge. Haruo Hosoya advanced his index *Z*, introduced the name "topological index", and gave a simpler and more general definition for *W* as the half-sum of all entries in the distance matrix **D** of the hydrogen-suppressed graph⁶. In this matrix, entries d_{ij} are topological distances along the shortest paths between vertices *i* and *j*, whereas in the adjacency matrix **A** en-

tries *v* are 1 for neighboring (adjacent) vertices and 0 otherwise. Row sums in the adjacency matrix are called vertex degrees v_i and row sums in the distance matrix are called distance sums s_i .

Although many more topological indices continued to be proposed, we shall discuss here only a few more indices.

(i) The average distance-based connectivity index *J*, known as the Balaban index, uses distance sums instead of vertex degrees and is averaged by the number *e* of edges and by the cyclomatic number (conventional number of rings) $R = E - n + 1$, where *n* is the number of graph vertices. It has a lower degeneracy than all previous topological indices⁶. Index *J* increases appreciably with branching, but the very slight increase with graph size is limited asymptotically : for an infinite path its value is the number $\pi = 3.14159...$ Because index *J* is practically normalized for graph size, it should not be

[†]In honour of Professor Padmakar V. Khadikar.

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used in mono parametric correlations with properties where the molecular size accounts for a significant part of the variance.

$$J = [E/(R + 1)] \sum_{\text{all edges}} (s_i \times s_j)^{-1/2} \quad (1)$$

(ii) For those properties where not only the "shape" but also the size of the graph influences the property/activity, two indices related to J have been developed. The first of these is index F , defined as :

$$F = E \sum_{\text{all edges}} (s_i \times s_j)^{-1/2} = J(R + 1). \quad (2)$$

This index is able to separate graph size, cyclicity, and branching¹¹.

(iii) The other J -related index, called index G , is more convenient for correlations. It is defined⁷ as :

$$\begin{aligned} G &= [n^2 E / (n + R + 1)] \sum_{\text{all edges}} (s_i \times s_j)^{-1/2} \\ &= n^2 J (R + 1) / (n + R + 1) \\ &= n^2 F / (n + R + 1). \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

It was found that two indices that had been described previously are well correlated with index G , namely the Kier-Hall index TOTOP, and the "triplet index" $DN^2S(4)$ ¹². The latter correlation is linear, whereas G and TOTOP are correlated parabolically.

In an earlier communication⁸ it was argued that understanding and predicting the chronic toxic effects of chemicals, especially carcinogenicity has become one of the major problem facing chemists involved with the development of industrial chemicals such as pesticides, drugs etc.; as well as scientist studying the toxicology of natural products. In yet another publication it was advocated that over the years chemists have been impressed by the great importance of hydrophobic effects in chemical-biological interactions as brought out by quantitative structure-activity relationships (QSAR). It seems timely to examine those instances where hydrophobic terms are not significant. All such approaches were non-topological in nature i.e. molecular descriptors other than topological indices were used in such investigations. In particular earlier we have used hydrophobic parameters. The Indian group, under the leadership of Khadikar reinvestigated such cases using distance-based connectivity topological indices and observed that better results are obtained even without using log P parameter⁴⁻¹².

Presentation of the data

Table 1 gives the parent structures of a set of 95 amines used while the activity log TA98 are listed in Table 2. Table 3 records the list of molecular descriptors used in modeling log TA98 activity. Table 4 lists the proposed models with their statistical parameters for modeling the activity. Table 5 record the correlation of the observed

Table 1. Parent structures used in the present study

Table 2. Name of the compounds and their mutagenicity			Table-2 (contd.)		
Compd. no.	Name of compounds	log TA98			
1	2-Bromo-7-aminofluorene	2.620	45	4-Fluoroaniline	-3.320
2	2-Methoxy-5-methylaniline (<i>p</i> -cresidine)	-2.050	46	9-Aminophenanthrene	2.980
3	5-Aminoquinoline	-2.000	47	3,3'-Diaminobiphenyl	-1.300
4	4-Ethoxyaniline (<i>p</i> -phenetidine)	-2.300	48	2-Aminopyrene	3.500
5	1-Aminonaphthalene	-0.600	49	2,6-Dichloro-1,4-phenylenediamine	-0.690
6	4-Aminofluorene	1.130	50	2-Amino-7-acetamidofluorene	1.180
7	2-Aminoanthracene	2.620	51	2,8-Diaminophenazine	1.120
8	7-Aminofluoranthene	2.880	52	6-Aminoquinoline	-2.670
9	8-Aminoquinoline	-1.140	53	4-Methoxy-2-methylaniline (<i>m</i> -cresidine)	-3.000
10	1,7-Diaminophenazine	0.750	54	3-Amino-2'-nitrophenyl	-1.300
11	2-Aminonaphthalene	-0.670	55	2,4'-Diaminobiphenyl	-0.920
12	4-Aminopyrene	3.160	56	1,6-Diaminophenazine	0.200
13	3-Amino-3'-nitrobiphenyl	-0.550	57	4-Aminophenyldisulfide	-1.030
14	2,4,5-Trimethylaniline	-1.320	58	2-Bromo-4,6-dinitroaniline	-0.540
15	3-Aminofluorene	0.890	59	2,4-Diamino- <i>n</i> -butylbenzene	-2.700
16	3,3'-Dichlorobenzidine	0.810	60	4-Aminophenylether	-1.140
17	2,4-Dimethylaniline (2,4-xylydine)	-2.220	61	2-Aminobiphenyl	-1.490
18	2,7-Diaminofluorene	0.480	62	1,9-Diaminophenazine	0.040
19	3-Aminofluoranthene	3.310	63	1-Aminofluorene	0.430
20	2-Aminofluorene	1.930	64	8-Aminofluoranthene	3.800
21	2-Amino-4'-nitrobiphenyl	-0.620	65	2-Chloroaniline	-3.000
22	4-Aminobiphenyl	-0.140	66	3-Amino- $\alpha\alpha\alpha$ -trifluorotoluene	-0.800
23	3-Methoxy-4-methylaniline (<i>o</i> -cresidine)	-1.960	67	2-Amino-1-nitronaphthalene	-1.170
24	2-Aminocarbazole	0.600	68	3-Amino-4'-nitrobiphenyl	0.690
25	2-Amino-5-nitrophenol	-2.520	69	4-Bromoaniline	-2.700
26	2,2'-Diaminobiphenyl	-1.520	70	2-Amino-4-chlorophenol	-3.000
27	2-Hydroxy-7-aminofluorene	0.410	71	3,3'-Dimethoxybenzidine	0.150
28	1-Aminophenanthrene	2.380	72	4-Cyclohexylaniline	-1.240
29	2,5-Dimethylaniline (2,5-xylydine)	-2.400	73	4-Phenoxyaniline	0.380
30	4-Amino 2'-nitrobiphenyl	-0.920	74	4,4'-Methylenebis (<i>o</i> -ethylaniline)	-0.990
31	2-Amino-4-methylphenol	-2.100	75	2-Amino-7-nitrofluorene	3.000
32	2-Aminophenazine	0.550	76	Benzidine	-0.390
33	4-Aminophenylsulfide	0.310	77	1-Amino-4-nitronaphthalene	-1.770
34	2,4-Dinitroaniline	-2.000	78	4-Amino-3'-nitrobiphenyl	1.020
35	2,4-Diaminoisopropylbenzene	-3.000	79	4-Amino-4'-nitrobiphenyl	1.040
36	2,4-Difluoroaniline	-2.700	80	1-Aminophenazine	-0.010
37	4,4'-Methylenedianiline	-1.600	81	4,4'-Methylenebis (<i>o</i> -fluoroaniline)	0.230
38	3,3'-Dimethylbenzidine	0.010	82	4-Chloro-2-nitroaniline	-2.220
39	2-Aminofluoranthene	3.230	83	3-Aminoquinoline	-3.140
40	2-Amino-3'-nitrobiphenyl	-0.890	84	3-Aminocarbazole	-0.480
41	1-Aminofluoranthene	3.350	85	4-Chloro-1,2-phenylenediamine	-0.490
42	4,4'-Ethylenebis(aniline)	-2.150	86	3-Aminophenanthrene	3.770
43	4-Chloroaniline	-2.520	87	3,4'-Diaminobiphenyl	0.200
44	2-Aminophenanthrene	2.460	88	1-Aminoanthracene	1.180
			89	1-Aminocarbazole	-1.040
			90	9-Aminoanthracene	0.870

Table-2 (contd.)

91	4-Aminocarbazole	-1.420
92	6-Aminochrysene	1.830
93	1-Aminopyrene	1.430
94	4,4'-Methylenbis (<i>o</i> -isopropylaniline)	-1.770
95	2,7-Diaminophenazine	3.970

Table-3 (contd.)

39	1.674	8.370	262.727
40	1.897	5.763	229.053
41	1.700	8.500	262.727
42	1.601	4.803	229.053
43	2.192	4.384	51.200
44	1.722	6.888	201.316
45	2.192	4.384	51.200
46	1.787	7.148	201.316
47	1.861	5.583	172.941
48	1.654	8.270	262.727
49	2.704	4.974	83.333
50	1.612	6.448	294.545
51	1.667	6.668	230.400
52	1.932	5.796	103.714
53	2.33	4.660	83.333
54	1.879	5.952	229.053
55	1.867	5.601	172.941
56	1.739	6.956	230.400
57	1.601	4.803	200.000
58	2.661	5.322	171.500
59	1.543	4.492	123.429
60	1.685	5.043	200.000
61	1.885	5.655	147.875
62	1.744	6.976	230.400
63	1.786	7.144	174.222
64	1.656	8.280	262.727
65	2.279	4.558	51.200
66	2.231	4.922	102.385
67	2.092	6.276	172.941
68	1.793	5.379	229.053
69	2.192	4.384	51.200
70	2.346	4.692	66.273
71	1.913	5.739	293.143
72	1.789	5.367	147.875
73	1.685	5.055	172.941
74	1.867	5.427	328.182
75	1.674	6.696	261.476
76	1.780	5.340	172.941
77	2.079	6.237	172.941
78	1.843	5.529	229.053
79	1.760	5.280	229.053
80	1.714	6.856	201.316
81	1.775	5.325	260.100
82	2.471	4.942	102.385
83	1.932	5.796	103.714
84	1.751	7.004	174.222

Table 3. Values of Balaban *J*, *F* and *G* indices

Compd. no.	<i>J</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>G</i>
1	1.722	6.888	201.316
2	2.356	4.712	83.333
3	1.993	5.979	103.714
4	2.132	4.264	83.333
5	1.993	5.979	103.714
6	1.800	7.200	174.222
7	1.673	6.692	201.316
8	1.694	8.470	262.727
9	1.993	5.979	103.714
10	1.701	6.804	230.400
11	1.932	5.796	103.714
12	1.692	8.460	262.727
13	1.879	5.637	229.053
14	2.462	4.924	83.333
15	1.751	7.004	174.222
16	1.884	5.583	172.941
17	2.346	4.692	66.273
18	1.722	6.888	201.316
19	1.679	8.395	262.727
20	1.739	6.956	174.222
21	1.867	5.496	229.053
22	1.789	5.367	147.875
23	2.376	4.752	83.333
24	1.739	6.956	174.222
25	2.396	4.792	102.385
26	1.963	5.889	172.941
27	1.722	6.888	201.316
28	1.763	7.052	201.316
29	2.346	4.692	66.273
30	1.944	5.832	229.053
31	2.346	4.692	66.273
32	1.673	6.692	201.316
33	1.685	5.055	172.941
34	2.526	5.052	146.467
35	1.940	4.874	102.385
36	2.346	4.692	66.273
37	1.681	5.043	200.000
38	1.884	5.652	229.053

Table-3 (contd.)

85	2.346	4.692	66.273
86	1.741	6.964	201.316
87	1.820	5.460	172.941
88	1.714	6.856	201.316
89	1.786	7.144	174.222
90	1.760	7.040	201.316
91	1.800	7.200	174.222
92	1.575	7.875	330.917
93	1.677	8.385	262.727
94	1.867	5.601	404.250
95	1.664	6.656	230.400

and estimated activities. Finally, Ridge parameters are given in Figs. 7-9.

Aim of the present study

The aim of current study is to investigate relative potential of newly proposed Balaban *F*, *G* and *J* indices in modeling the mutagenic activity of 95 compounds listed in Table 1 by using maximum-R² method¹³. The mutagenic activity was adopted from our earlier study. All the three topological indices were calculated using the DRAGON software¹⁴ and the structure optimization was done using Hyperchem¹⁵ as well as ACD Lab software¹⁶. The results are finally discussed using Ridge parameters.

Table 4. Proposed models

Model	Eq. no.	Parameter (s)	R ²	Se	R ² _{Adj}	F	Q
1	4	<i>G</i>	0.4119	1.4841	-	65.141	0.4324
2	5	<i>G</i> and <i>F</i>	0.6703	1.1172	0.6632	93.529	0.7328
3	6	<i>G</i> , <i>F</i> and <i>J</i>	0.6805	1.1059	0.6700	64.610	0.7515

Table 5. Observed vs estimated log TA98 values using eqs. (4-6) (Models 1-3, Table 4)

Compd. no.	Obs. log TA98	Using eq. (4)		Using eq. (5)		Using eq. (6)	
		Est. log TA98	Residual	Est. log TA98	Residual	Est. log TA98	Residual
1	2.620	0.204	2.416	0.916	1.704	1.008	1.612
2	-2.050	-1.796	-0.254	-2.202	0.152	-2.364	0.314
3	-2.000	-1.451	-0.549	-0.694	-1.306	-0.609	-1.391
4	-2.300	-1.796	-0.504	-2.689	0.389	-2.561	0.261
5	-0.600	-1.451	0.851	-0.694	0.094	-0.609	0.009
6	1.130	-0.255	1.385	1.083	0.047	1.119	0.011
7	2.620	0.204	2.416	0.703	1.917	0.867	1.753
8	2.880	1.246	1.634	3.027	-0.147	2.875	0.005
9	-1.140	-1.451	0.311	-0.694	-0.446	-0.609	-0.531
10	0.750	0.698	0.052	1.010	-0.260	1.07	-0.32
11	-0.670	-1.451	0.781	-0.893	0.223	-0.724	0.054
12	3.160	1.246	1.914	3.016	0.144	2.867	0.293
13	-0.550	0.675	-1.225	-0.268	-0.282	-0.299	-0.251
14	-1.320	-1.796	0.476	-1.971	0.651	-2.27	0.95
15	0.890	-0.255	1.145	0.870	0.020	0.978	-0.088
16	0.810	-0.277	1.087	-0.684	1.494	-0.568	1.378
17	-2.220	-2.086	-0.134	-2.332	0.112	-2.444	0.224
18	0.480	0.204	0.276	0.916	-0.436	1.008	-0.528
19	3.310	1.246	2.064	2.946	0.364	2.817	0.493
20	1.930	-0.255	2.185	0.817	1.113	0.944	0.986
21	-0.620	0.675	-1.295	-0.422	-0.198	-0.387	-0.233
22	-0.140	-0.702	0.562	-1.079	0.939	-0.808	0.668
23	-1.960	-1.796	-0.164	-2.158	0.198	-2.346	0.386
24	0.600	-0.255	0.855	0.817	-0.217	0.944	-0.344

Table-5 (contd.)

25	-2.520	-1.473	-1.047	-1.993	-0.527	-2.249	-0.271
26	-1.520	-0.277	-1.243	-0.351	-1.169	-0.376	-1.144
27	0.410	0.204	0.206	0.916	-0.506	1.008	-0.598
28	2.380	0.204	2.176	1.094	1.286	1.126	1.254
29	-2.400	-2.086	-0.314	-2.332	-0.068	-2.444	0.044
30	-0.920	0.675	-1.595	-0.056	-0.864	-0.177	-0.743
31	-2.100	-2.086	-0.014	-2.332	0.232	-2.444	0.344
32	0.550	0.204	0.346	0.703	-0.153	0.867	-0.317
33	0.310	-0.277	0.587	-1.258	1.568	-0.898	1.208
34	-2.000	-0.726	-1.274	-1.430	-0.570	-1.95	-0.05
35	-3.000	-1.473	-1.527	-1.904	-1.096	-2.213	-0.787
36	-2.700	-2.086	-0.614	-2.332	-0.368	-2.444	-0.256
37	-1.600	0.182	-1.782	-1.099	-0.501	-0.792	-0.808
38	0.010	0.675	-0.665	-0.252	0.262	-0.29	0.3
39	3.230	1.246	1.984	2.919	0.311	2.798	0.432
40	-0.890	0.675	-1.565	-0.131	-0.759	-0.22	-0.67
41	3.350	1.246	2.104	3.060	0.290	2.898	0.452
42	-2.150	0.675	-2.825	-1.175	-0.975	-0.821	-1.329
43	-2.520	-2.341	-0.179	-2.763	0.243	-2.642	0.122
44	2.460	0.204	2.256	0.916	1.544	1.008	1.452
45	-3.320	-2.341	-0.979	-2.763	-0.557	-2.642	-0.678
46	2.980	0.204	2.776	1.199	1.781	1.195	1.785
47	-1.300	-0.277	-1.023	-0.684	-0.616	-0.568	-0.732
48	3.500	1.246	2.254	2.810	0.690	2.72	0.78
49	-0.690	-1.796	1.106	-1.917	1.227	-2.248	1.558
50	1.180	1.786	-0.606	1.031	0.149	1.082	0.098
51	1.120	0.698	0.422	0.862	0.258	0.972	0.148
52	-2.670	-1.451	-1.219	-0.893	-1.777	-0.724	-1.946
53	-3.000	-1.796	-1.204	-2.258	-0.742	-2.387	-0.613
54	-1.300	0.675	-1.975	0.074	-1.374	-0.102	-1.198
55	-0.920	-0.277	-0.643	-0.665	-0.255	-0.556	-0.364
56	0.200	0.698	-0.498	1.175	-0.975	1.179	-0.979
57	-1.030	0.182	-1.212	-1.360	0.330	-0.943	-0.087
58	-0.540	-0.301	-0.239	-0.977	0.437	-1.727	1.187
59	-2.700	-1.116	-1.584	-2.186	-0.514	-2.293	-0.407
60	-1.140	0.182	-1.322	-1.099	-0.041	-0.792	-0.348
61	-1.490	-0.702	-0.788	-0.765	-0.725	-0.627	-0.863
62	0.040	0.698	-0.658	1.197	-1.157	1.193	-1.153
63	0.430	-0.255	0.685	1.022	-0.592	1.079	-0.649
64	3.800	1.246	2.554	2.821	0.979	2.728	1.072
65	-3.000	-2.341	-0.659	-2.574	-0.426	-2.566	-0.434
66	-0.800	-1.473	0.673	-1.852	1.052	-2.192	1.392
67	-1.170	-0.277	-0.893	0.070	-1.240	-0.134	-1.036
68	0.690	0.675	0.015	-0.549	1.239	-0.46	1.15
69	-2.700	-2.341	-0.359	-2.763	0.063	-2.642	-0.058
70	-3.000	-2.086	-0.914	-2.332	-0.668	-2.444	-0.556

Table-5 (contd.)

71	0.150	1.762	-1.612	0.251	-0.101	0.033	0.117
72	-1.240	-0.702	-0.538	-1.079	-0.161	-0.808	-0.432
73	0.380	-0.277	0.657	-1.258	1.638	-0.898	1.278
74	-0.990	2.356	-3.346	0.134	-1.124	-0.016	-0.974
75	3.000	1.225	1.775	1.090	1.910	1.122	1.878
76	-0.390	-0.277	-0.113	-0.948	0.558	-0.72	0.33
77	-1.770	-0.277	-1.493	0.027	-1.797	-0.158	-1.612
78	1.020	0.675	0.345	-0.386	1.406	-0.367	1.387
79	1.040	0.675	0.365	-0.657	1.697	-0.522	1.562
80	-0.010	0.204	-0.214	0.881	-0.891	0.985	-0.995
81	0.230	1.201	-0.971	-0.410	0.640	-0.364	0.594
82	-2.220	-1.473	-0.747	-1.830	-0.390	-2.183	-0.037
83	-3.140	-1.451	-1.689	-0.893	-2.247	-0.724	-2.416
84	-0.480	-0.255	-0.225	0.870	-1.350	0.978	-1.458
85	-0.490	-2.086	1.596	-2.332	1.842	-2.444	1.954
86	3.770	0.204	3.566	0.998	2.772	1.063	2.707
87	0.200	-0.277	0.477	-0.818	1.018	-0.644	0.844
88	1.180	0.204	0.976	0.881	0.299	0.985	0.195
89	-1.040	-0.255	-0.785	1.022	-2.062	1.079	-2.119
90	0.870	0.204	0.666	1.081	-0.211	1.118	-0.248
91	-1.420	-0.255	-1.165	1.083	-2.503	1.119	-2.539
92	1.830	2.402	-0.572	2.814	-0.984	2.699	-0.869
93	1.430	1.246	0.184	2.935	-1.505	2.809	-1.379
94	-1.770	3.646	-5.416	0.808	-2.578	0.411	-2.181
95	3.970	0.698	3.272	0.916	1.704	0.963	3.007

Fig. 1. Correlation of J with F.

Results and discussion

Comparison and correlations between the topological indices : J, G and F

We explored if there is any correlation between indices

J, F, and G. From Figs. 1-3 one can see that there is a satisfactory correlation with $R^2 = 0.586$ between J and F for all the above 95 compounds. For the same compounds, still better correlations exist between J and G ($R^2 = 0.6351$) as well as between G and F ($R^2 = 0.7041$).

Fig. 2. Correlation of J with G.

Fig. 3. Correlation of G with F.

Modeling of log TA98

We now discuss the modeling of mutagenic activity log TA98 using most appropriate one, two, and three-variable models.

(i) Modeling of mutagenic activity (log TA98) using one-variable modeling

For the entire set of 95 compounds the best one-variable model was obtained with the following results :

$$\log \text{TA98} = 0.0170 (\pm 0.0021)G - 3.2096$$

$$N = 95, R^2 = 0.4119, \text{Se} = 1.4841, F = 65.141, Q = 0.4324 \quad (4)$$

Here, and here after n - is the number of compound; Se - is the standard error of estimation, R^2 - is the multiple correlation coefficient; R^2_A - is the adjusted R^2 ; F - is the Fishers statistics and Q - is the Pogliani's quality factor¹⁷⁻¹⁹ which is the ratio of R and Se . The positive coefficient of

G indicates that log TA98 increases with increase in the magnitude of *G*.

(ii) Modeling of mutagenic activity (log TA98) using two-variable modeling

The successive regression indicated that a quality of the above model is improved by the addition of the parameter *F*. The resulting model is found as below :

$$\log \text{TA98} = 1.0876 (\pm 0.1281) F + 0.0064 (\pm 0.0020) G - 7.8570$$

$$N = 95, R^2 = 0.6703, R^2_A = 0.6632, \text{Se} = 1.1172, F = 93.529, Q = 0.7328 \quad (5)$$

Here, coefficients of both the correlating parameters *G* and *F* are positive indicating that the magnitude of log TA98 increases linearly with the increased magnitude of *G* and *F*.

(iii) Modeling of mutagenic activity (log TA98) using three-variable modeling

Finally, a three-variable model with the following results is obtained for modeling log TA98 :

$$\log \text{TA98} = 0.9978 (\pm 0.1373) F + 0.0042 (\pm 0.0004) G - 1.1157 (\pm 0.6548) J - 4.7852$$

$$N = 95, R^2 = 0.6805, R^2_A = 0.6700, \text{Se} = 1.1059, F = 64.610, Q = 0.7515 \quad (6)$$

The above model indicates that decrease in the extended connectivity (*J*) increases the exhibition of log TA98.

Predictive power of the model

It is worth mentioning that statistically excellent model does not necessary mean that it will also have excellent predictive power. Hence, we have investigated the predictive power of proposed model. There are two different ways to investigate the predictive power of the model. First one consists of calculating Pogliani quality factor¹⁷⁻¹⁹, *Q*. This quality factor *Q* is defined as the ratio of correlation coefficient to its standard error of estimation i.e. $Q = R/\text{Se}$. Thus, higher the value of *R*, the lower the *Se*, the greater will be the value of *Q* and more will be the predictive power of the model. The calculated values of *Q* presented with the proposed models indicates that the predictive potential of the models goes on increasing as we pass from one-variable to three-variable model. Still better way of deciding predictive power of the model is to calculate predictive correlation coefficient i.e. R^2_{Pred} . This can be done by calculating the mutagenic activity (log TA98) from the proposed models and comparing the same with the experimental activity. Such a comparison is shown in Table 5 and demonstrated in Figs. 4-6.

Fig. 4. Correlation between observed and estimated log TA98 using Model 1 (eq. (4)).

Fig. 5. Correlation between obs. log TA98 vs est. log TA98 values using Model 2 (eq. (5)).

Fig. 6. Correlation between obs. log TA98 vs est. log TA98 values using Model 3 (eq. (6)).

Fig. 7. Ridge statistics showing probability and residual plots.

Fig. 8. Variance inflation plot.

The R^2_{Pred} values are found to be 0.4119, 0.6703, and 0.6805 respectively for these equations showing that these models, more or less, have similar predictive power and that the model with *G* and *F* as the correlating parameters has slightly better predictive power.

Comments on R^2_A

At this stage it will be very interesting to comment on R^2_A i.e. adjusted- R^2 , which takes into account the adjustment of R^2 . If variable is added that does not contribute its fair share, the R^2_A will actually decline. R^2 may appear artificially high if the number of variables is high compared to the sample size (i.e. the number of compound present in the computed model). Furthermore, R^2_A is a measure of the % explained variation in the dependent

variable that takes into account the relationship between the number of cases and the number of independent variables in the regression model. Where as R^2 will always increase when an independent variable is added. R^2_A will decrease if the added variable doesn't reduce the unexplained variable enough to offset the loss of decreases of freedom.

In cases when we have only used *G* for modeling log TA98 we obtained $R^2_A = 0.4056$ which goes on increasing with two- and three-variable modeling. This means that the added independent variables have enough contribution to the proposed models.

Effect due to co-linearity

From the results and discussion made above we ob-

Fig. 9. Ridge plot.

served that the models expressed by eqs. (4), (5) and (6) are best suited for modeling log TA98. The correlating parameters used there in are all derived from J index. It is therefore, necessary to examine the existence of co-linearity defect, if any, in these models. If such defect exists then we will use the recommendation of Randic²⁰ for explaining it. However, at present the best way to examine such a defect is to obtain correlation matrix for the parameters involved in these models. Such correlation matrix is shown in Table 6. A perusal of this Table shows that G and F are linearly correlated. This means

	log TA98	J	F	G
log TA98	1			
J	-0.665	1		
F	0.797	-0.657	1	
G	0.642	-0.727	0.619	1

that this model may suffer from the defect due to co-linearity. However, the Ridge analysis has indicated that due to VIF there exists such co-linearity defect, but the condition number says such defects do not exist. It means for arriving at the final decision we have to take care of Randic recommendations²⁰. We can, therefore, apply Randic recommendations²⁰ for explaining favorable recom-

mendations for the use of two- and three-variable models for modeling log TA98.

According to Randic, under certain situations even highly correlated descriptors could be retained in the model. We will, therefore, use Randic's recommendations²⁰ in the present case also. Randic stated that if a descriptor strongly correlates with another descriptor already used in a regression, such a descriptor in most studies should be discarded. For example ${}^1\chi$ and ${}^2\chi$, ${}^1\chi$ often strongly correlate and in many structure-property-activity studies ${}^2\chi$ has been discarded. This is not theoretically justified and despite the widespread practice should be stopped. Although two highly correlated descriptors overall depict the same features of molecular structure, it is important to recognize that even highly interrelated descriptors differ in some other structural traits. The difference between them may be relatively small but nevertheless very important for structure-property relationship.

Conclusion

From the results and discussion made above, we observed that using newly proposed Balaban G and F indices we can successfully model, mentor, and model log TA98.

Experimental

(i) *Mutagenic activity (log TA98)* : The mutagenic activity namely log TA98 is the same as used in our earlier paper²¹ .

(ii) *Topological indices* : All the three topological indices were calculated from the hydrogen suppressed molecular graphs of aromatic and hetero-aromatic amines using DRAGON software¹⁴ and the structure optimization is made using Hyperchem¹⁵ and ACD Labs¹⁶ software.

(iii) *Regression analysis* : In modeling log TA98 the method of maximum-R² is adopted¹⁴. The regression analysis is done using NCSS program.

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